

FOSTERING EQUITY AND EXCELLENCE THROUGH COOPERATIVE LEARNING

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"Education is at the heart of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and essential for the success of all Sustainable Development Goals. Highlighting education as a stand-alone goal, SDG4-Education 2030 ensures inclusive and equitable quality education and promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all (United Nations, 2015). The goal of 'Education for All' has been high on the agenda of the Government of India since the adoption of the Constitution of India in 1950 and the commencement of development planning since 1951. Successive development policies and five-year plans have pursued this goal during the last six decades. Substantial progress towards the Education for All goals has been made during the past few years.

India faces two challenges with regard to academic achievement: one is inculcating knowledge and skills necessary for success in the 21st Century, and the other is minimizing the difference in educational achievement between students of different communities and different income status. The first crisis is a crisis in excellence; the second crisis is a crisis in equity. Both these two challenges are felt like crisis because education occupies a strategic position in India's development priorities with the growing demands of competitive global economy and the growing inequality which can lead to failure in democracy.

Lack of educational equity disrupts the elements of a true democracy. The health of a democracy depends on its ability to fully develop the potential of all students. Democracy requires wise decisions made not by some voters, but by all voters. Failure to meet these two challenges — creating schools of excellence and schools of equity — undercuts the ability to realize core values, the ability to prosper economically, and the ability to meet the needs of present students and future generations. India is a country of plurality. India stands committed to providing quality education and providing relevant skills to its children irrespective of region, caste or community. Providing free and compulsory education to all children is a goal that is enshrined in the Indian Constitution as a Fundamental Right.

Equity and Excellence

Equity with excellence is the keystone of a transformative education agenda. In order to build on this corner stone all forms of exclusion and marginalization, disparities and inequalities in access, participation and learning outcomes should be addressed. No education target should be considered met unless met by all. Excellence without equity risks leading to large economic and social disparities; equity at the expense of quality is a meaningless aspiration (OECD, 2013c).

Equity and Excellence are two of the four Es of mutually supporting strategic priorities in education on which approach to education development is based. The other two Es are Expansion and Employability (NUEPA 2015). Achieving excellence by improving the quality and relevance of education and enabling all children and young people to achieve expected/specified learning outcomes remains

a key goal of education sector development programmes in India. The core elements of the strategy for achieving excellence include:

- (i) strengthening the quality of teaching-learning processes through comprehensive concerted large scale efforts with simultaneous attention to how these processes translate into better outcomes;
- (ii) enhancing the motivation, capacity and accountability of teachers for improving learning outcomes at all levels;
- (iii) improving governance of educational institutions through institutional focus on quality, based on principles of autonomy, accountability and performance, along with measures for re-defining the recruitment criteria, eligibility of teachers and merit-based processes of recruitment in these institutions;
- (iv) encouraging innovations and diversity of approaches in matters of curricula, pedagogies and community engagements in order to respond to the diversity of learner groups, and
- (v) strengthening the monitoring and accountability mechanisms.

The focus of equity/inclusion is on bridging the gender and social category gaps in participation in education. It recognises the right of every individual to education without discrimination on any grounds and according priority to education of the excluded, vulnerable, under-served and other disadvantaged groups. The main thrust is to ensure that educational opportunities are available for and accessible to all segments of the society. The approaches include special initiatives for enhancing access to quality education for disadvantaged and weaker sections of the community such as the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, other backward classes, children belonging to Muslim community and differently-abled children. The focus on equity and inclusion also envisages approaches that would help meet the learning needs of diverse groups of pupils and provide opportunities for all learners to become successful in their learning experiences.

Equity in education can be seen through two dimensions: fairness and inclusion (OECD 2007). Equity as fairness implies that personal or socio-economic circumstances, such as gender, ethnic origin or family background, are not obstacles to success in education. Equity as inclusion means ensuring that all students reach at least a basic minimum level of skills. Equitable education systems are fair and inclusive, and support their students in reaching their learning potential without either formally or informally erecting barriers or lowering expectations. Bridging social and intellectual group gaps in access to and participation in education is a non-discriminatory approach in education. The Programmatic interventions to reduce social category gap in education pursued within the mainstream elementary education system should be without sacrificing the quality of education. That is equity should not be at the expense of excellence.

Cooperative Learning- the Proven Tool

The Instructional Solution to accelerate both excellence and equity is the use of a time tested, simple yet powerful tool: A research proven, school-tested solution. Cooperative learning is a complex pedagogical undertaking that has the potential to foster both individual content learning and mutual respect between peers (O'Donnell & Hmelo-Silver, 2013; Webb & Farivar, 1994). In cooperative classroom culture, all students share responsibility for the success. Teachers give the necessary support, time and resources and diagnose students' learning needs and plan and evaluate teaching programmes and strategies. Cooperative learning is commonly illustrated when groups of students work together to search for understanding, meaning, or solutions or to create an artifact or product of their learning (Hattie, J. (2015). The learning activities include cooperative writing, group projects, joint problem solving, debates, study teams, and other activities.

The cooperative Learning is a powerful strategy to ensure equity in classroom performance and achievement. Cooperative learning is not new. It is rooted in Lev Vygotsky's (Taber, K. S. 2011) concept of learning called social constructivism in which he highlighted the importance of learning

through communication and interactions with others rather than just through independent work. This has made way for the ideas of group learning, one of which being cooperative learning.

Characterizing the equity and excellence dynamics of a cooperative learning situation, then, call for an analysis of the research findings that supports cooperative learning over traditional ones. **The Objective of the study**

The objective of the study is to assess the efficacy of Cooperative learning approach for making equity and excellence in education. With this objective in view research questions were formulated to focus the study on the objective.

Research questions:

1. Does Cooperative learning help to foster equity in education?
2. Does Cooperative learning help to foster excellence in education?

Method of study

The method adopted for the study is to explore the empirical studies conducted on cooperative learning with research questions in view

Sources of the Data: the data for the present study were collected from secondary sources available from books and internet.

Cooperative class rooms: empirical studies

The Riverside Cooperative Learning Study by Kagan, S. Zahn, G. L., Widaman, K., Schwarzwald, J. & Tyrrell, G., (1985) demonstrated cooperative learning produced more inclusive classrooms. This was revealed by several measures, including measures of cooperativeness of students, class climate, self-esteem, and ethnic relations. Students taught with cooperative learning became more cooperative: When presented with alternatives, they more often chose to enhance rather than diminish the outcomes of their classmates. Rating of social climate, as measured by standardized class climate measures, improved markedly for minority students in cooperative learning classrooms. A variety of other outcomes of the Riverside Study support the general conclusion that minority students fare far better in cooperative learning classrooms. Attitudes toward schoolwork and social climate were more favorable in the cooperative learning classrooms for all students.

The most dramatic finding, however, was a radical transformation of race relations. To test race relations, students were asked a number of questions that revealed their level of intimacy with each of their classmates. Questions included low-level intimacy questions (willingness to sit next to a student; willingness to loan him or her a pencil) and high-level intimacy questions (willingness to be best friends; willingness to invite him or her home). The results were dramatic. In traditional classrooms, self-segregation among students became more intense with each year in school. Increasingly, students were not willing to be friends or even be friendly with others outside their own race. In contrast, in classrooms in which cooperative learning was used, the tendency of students to choose friends only among their own racial groups practically disappeared.

In the traditional classes, there was a slight tendency for the minority and majority students to manifest more friendliness toward others of their own group. By grades 5 and 6, this slight ethnic cleavage became an enormous chasm: Being of the same ethnicity became almost a prerequisite for friendship. In marked contrast, there was no significant ethnic cleavage at either grade level in the classrooms that included cooperative student teams. Cooperative instructional practices create an inclusive classroom climate in which self-esteem and positive race-relations blossom. That climate improves academic achievement for all students, especially for students who otherwise are likely to be excluded and alienated. Students who feel more accepted and included are more likely to participate, ask for and offer help to peers, and receive peer encouragement for achievement. A more inclusive classroom and higher self-esteem predict more participation, which in turn boosts engagement and

achievement. Students who feel more liked and accepted and who are more confident are more likely to participate, feeling less fear of failure. Greater participation is built into the cooperative learning structures (Kagan, S., 2010).

Beginning in the early grades, low achieving and minority students are less likely to participate and to risk failure in front of the whole class in traditional classrooms that lack a supportive, inclusive class climate. Not receiving as much practice or reward, they become even lower achieving, more alienated, and even less likely to participate. So, as they progress through the grades, lower achieving students in traditional classrooms increasingly leave it to the high achieving students to raise their hands to be called on. With each successive grade, lower achievers progressively drop out psychologically, participating less and less. Finally, psychological dropout converts to physical dropout.

In the study by Kenneth T. Keith J., Topping D. Christie C. Donaldso C. and Emma J., Kay L., (2010) there is conflicting evidence how group work leads to improved classroom relations. A before and after design was used to measure the impact on work and play relations of a cooperative learning programme in single- and mixed-age classes across urban and rural schools. Data were also collected on student interactions and teacher ratings of their group-work skills. Analysis of variance revealed significant gains for both types of relation. Multilevel modeling indicated that better work relations were the product of improving group skills, which offset tensions produced by transactive dialogue, and this effect fed through in turn to play relations. Although before intervention rural children were familiar with each other neither this nor age mix affected outcomes. The results suggest the social benefits of cooperative learning are a separate outcome of group work, rather than being either a pre-condition for, or a direct consequence of successful activity, but that initial training in group skills may serve to enhance these benefits.

However researches consistently find cooperative learning dramatically improving student achievement in all subject areas, at all grades, and, most importantly, for all groups of students. Summarizing research-based strategies for increasing student achievement, noted educational research team, Marzano, Pickering, & Pollock (2001) found cooperative learning has the best, largest empirical base. "Of all classroom grouping strategies, cooperative learning may be the most flexible and powerful", says, Ellis & Fouts (2003)

In the traditional classroom, those students who least need the practice are called for response, and those who most need the practice are least called! When cooperative learning structures are used, the teacher calls on all students to respond to the same question presented, having them engage in Pair Share. In the same amount of time that a teacher in the traditional classroom can call on and respond to three or four students, each giving one response, the teacher using cooperative learning structures has every student in the class give several answers! (Slavin, R. E.1977).

Group Composition and Performance study on Equity Issues in cooperative Group Assessment conducted by Noreen M. Webb, Kariane M. Nemer, Alexander W. Chizhik (1998) investigated the effects of group ability composition on group processes and outcomes in science performance assessments. Students in eighth-grade science classes worked on science assessments first individually, then in groups, and finally individually again. The result of the study showed that group composition had a major impact on group discussion quality and on student achievement. Groups with above-average students produced more accurate and high-quality performance than groups without above-average students. As a result, below-average students who worked with above-average students showed higher achievement than did below-average students who worked without above-average students. The study also revealed that heterogeneous groups provide a greater benefit for below-average students than for above average students.

Niral Shah, Colleen Lewis Roxane Caires, (2013) Analyzed Equity in cooperative Learning Situations. Their paper presents a comparative case study of the different ways that equity and

inequity emerged as an elementary computer science student collaborated with two different classmates on programming tasks. Data collected include audio recordings of students' interactions, field notes, written assessments, and students' digital work. Findings indicate that despite the existence of participation structures designed to foster equitable collaboration, inequities emerged as students positioned themselves and their classmates with identities as more or less competent in computer science. While in the first dyad this positioning was often overt, in the second dyad positioning assumed a more passive form. Further, there is evidence that these positioning had an impact on students' opportunities to learn.

STAD. Student Teams Achievement Divisions (STAD) is a cooperative learning method that has students practice in teams to master academic content. They earn points for their team by improving their achievement compared to their usual level of achievement. The lower achieving minority students did dramatically better, closing the achievement gap! Each teammate leaves the team, and works with like-topic members from other teams. Students then return to teach their teammates their portion of the content. The result that all students learned equally well in competitive classes. Using a different cooperative learning method, with a different student population, at a different grade level, in a different part of the country, and with a different curriculum content, the same result obtained (Kagan, S. & Kagan, M. n (2009).

Mills Hill Elementary School in England has posted extremely dramatic gains in excellence and equity by adopting Kagan Cooperative Learning Structures. As part of a leadership team cross-school survey of the impact of cooperative learning, 14 teachers attributed the gains to the peer support in cooperative learning compared to the isolation and alienation created by traditional instructional strategies. Some teachers were choked up as they described the transformation resulting from cooperative learning: "It was a real lump in your throat moment; they'd say, 'before you just sat there and you didn't know what was going on and you were frightened to ask, but now you can just ask your friends, or ask your team'. You just got an idea of how that child had been going through school and you just don't realise; it was a very powerful moment."

Students at Mills Hill explained the power of cooperative learning quite simply: "Working with my team helped me do things I couldn't on my own. We did this thing on our table called Rally Robin and you talk with your partner and take turns in sharing ideas." The failure to create engagement among all students in the traditional classroom extends beyond Question-Answer time. During independent practice, students are on their own. With little to no support, they often find repeated worksheet work boring or difficult, and often tune out. In contrast, students in the cooperative learning classroom are placed in teams. The instructional strategies are designed so that students are on the same side as their teammate; there is a high degree of interaction; everyone is held individually accountable for participating.

In engaging students take turns responding, receiving encouragement and praise, and tutoring if necessary. Students keep each other engaged. It is this greater engagement of all students that best explains the increased excellence and equity found. The dramatic, intense engagement among all students indicates the remarkable outcomes of cooperative learning research. Structural conditions encourage full and equal participation for all students. Plus students have the support of their peers. Simply put, cooperative learning engages every student while traditional instruction engages a select few.

The foregone discussion validate the effectiveness of cooperative learning for accelerating both excellence and equity. The merits of cooperative learning include celebration of diversity by which students learn to work with all types of people. During small-group interactions, they find many opportunities to reflect upon and reply to the diverse responses fellow learners bring to the questions raised. Groups also allow students to add their perspectives to an issue based on their cultural differences. This exchange inevitably helps students to better understand other cultures and point of view:

Diversity of the groups has an enriching effect. Students work with all types of individuals. Different students will have a variety of responses to the questions raised. Multi-Modal Stimulus Input and novelty of presentations caters to the individual differences of the students. Each student can address the diverse responses fellow learners bring based on their cultural differences and experiences and can add their perspectives.

Cooperative learning provides room for Constructive Interdependence of the students, Individual Responsibility, Equal Involvement of all the participants, and Synchronized Interface among students

Students learn to relate to their peers and other learners as they work together in group enterprises. This can be especially helpful for students who have difficulty with social skills. They can benefit from structured interactions with others.

Acknowledgment of individual differences. When questions are raised, different students will have a variety of responses. Each of these can help the group create a product that reflects a wide range of perspectives and is thus more complete and comprehensive. Instruction Tailored to Individual Differences in Intelligences and Learning Styles promotes active involvement of students. Each student has opportunities to contribute in groups. Students are apt to take more ownership of their material and to think critically about related issues when they work as a team.

Because there are more exchanges among students in groups, students receive more personal feedback about their ideas and responses. This constructive personal feedback also boosts up their self-concept.

Findings of the study

From the discussion of the empirical studies conducted on cooperative learning the following pointed have been generated:

- Cooperative Learning produced more inclusive classrooms compared to traditional teaching
- Minority students fared far better performances in Cooperative Learning
- Cooperative Learning Improves race relations with no ethnic cleavage
- Social benefits of group work and group skills influence better work relations
- Group composition and group discussion quality impacts on student achievement
- Below-average students benefit from heterogeneous groups but above average students do not show significant benefit.
- Positioning has positive impact on students' learning opportunities
- Lower achieving minority students show improvement on achievement in Team learning
- Peer support has positive effect on excellence and equity
- Greater engagement of all students in the class has higher impact on the excellence and equity.

Studies conducted globally suggest that Cooperative learning fosters excellence and equity in education.

The characteristic features of cooperative learning that promotes excellence and equity are: Celebration of diversity; Multi-Modal Stimulus Input; Novelty of presentations; Constructive Interdependence; Individual Responsibility; Equal Involvement; Synchronized Interface; structured interactions; Acknowledgment of individual differences and Constructive Personal Feedback.

The single most important influence on students' achievement and progress is the effectiveness of the teaching they receive (Alton-Lee, A. (2003). The enormous body of research, affirms with great confidence, that cooperative learning is a powerful antidote to lagging achievement and the achievement gap.

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